

Job Design Dimensions and Its Impact on Knowledge Sharing Among Employees in Jordanians Hospitals in Irbid District – Jordan

Dr Ahmad Al Azzam
Jadara University, Irbid, Jordan

Abstract:

Job design is a field of concern among researchers as one of human resource management in addition knowledge sharing among employees also has more concern as well, so the aim of this study is to examine the impact of job design dimensions on knowledge sharing among employees in health care establishments in Jordan, job design dimensions include autonomy, task identity, and feedback, the study sample consists of hospitals located in Irbid city in the northern province of Jordan, the study results reveal that there is an impact of job design dimensions on knowledge sharing among employees, the study found that these dimensions act as motivators for employees to seek knowledge sharing by themselves in order to accomplish their tasks, the study has put some recommendations.

Key words: Human resources, Knowledge sharing, Job autonomy, Task identity, Feedback, Jordanian hospitals.

1. INTRODUCTION

Job design is an important field of concern because of its effect in motivating employees to enhance and improve their performance [1]. It has an important role in knowledge sharing among employees in organizations. Therefore, it plays a basic and important role in knowledge sharing. Additionally, organizations who need to spread knowledge among their employees have to focus on job design dimensions to keep a good level knowledge sharing among employees. The idea behind job design dimensions impact on knowledge sharing in organizations is not a new one. Many scholars see that those results of job design like specialization may negatively affect knowledge sharing among employees because of deep differences in the level of knowledge insights between specialized and non-specialized employees [2]. Management in organizations may design jobs in organizations in a way to act as a motivator for knowledge sharing among employees.

Research problem

Employee turnover is a major problem faces organizations because when employees specialize in a certain field of knowledge, many competitors try to recruit them, in such cases human resource managers have to find a solution to this issue.

To keep knowledge of these experienced people in the organization by letting all employees in organization acquired this knowledge by sharing it with them. Therefore, by doing so, the organization can retain the needed knowledge. Sharing knowledge between employees can be enhanced through clever design of jobs in organizations, to examine this assumption.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

This research aims to achieve following research objectives:

- To identify the level of relationship between job design elements and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals
- To explore the level of relationship between job autonomy and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals
- To analyze the level of relationship between task identity and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals
- To examine the level of relationship between job feedback and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals

Research Question

This study is trying to find answers to the following questions:

- What is the level of relationship between job design elements and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals?
- What is the level of relationship between job autonomy and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals?
- What is the level of relationship between task identity and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals?
- What is the level of relationship between job feedback and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals?

Scope of the study:

This study has been carried out in public and private hospitals in Irbid district in the northern province of Jordan. The study

can be implemented in the context of Irbid district in the northern province of Jordan to improve the conditions of hospitals operating in this region.

Study hypothesis:

To answer the study questions the researcher has formulated the following hypothesis:

H0-1 There is no significant correlation between job design and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals at Irbid district

H0-2 There is no significant correlation between job autonomy and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals at Irbid district

Ho-3 There is no significant correlation between task identity and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals at Irbid district

Ho-4 There is no significant correlation between job feedback and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals at Irbid district

Study Model

Relying on the literature review and the previous studies the researcher has developed the study model, which it is, consists of the dependent variable (knowledge sharing) and the independent variable (job design dimensions). The independent variable has three sub-variables (job autonomy, job identity, and job feedback).

Independent variable

Dependent variable

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Job design dimensions

Job design is one of the important tasks of human resources management; job design means identifying duties, tasks, and responsibility of the job, meanwhile, the conventional concept of job design is concentrating on the job itself instead of on an employee who performs the job. Although some researchers still considering the motivational effect of job design on employees because of the psychological effect of job specifications reflected on employees practices, in this aspect the literature focus on three dimensions as follows [1].

- Job has a certain meaning through experience
- Job has responsibilities related to work results

- Feedback about work performance is important to employees

According to Fuller, Marker & Hester, the job mentioned above design dimensions will create a factual in organizations [3]. While Grant, see that job must have a social impact in which it enhances self-confidence for employees and respect from others when they perform their job in a right manner, also job design dimensions [4]. According to Hackman and Oldham, (1976) are acting as a motivator for employees [3].

Job design is built upon job analysis and career path analysis, job design and job analysis are considered to be an introduction to recruiting, examining, and hiring of employees in organizations, job design imply description and definition of job context, job specifications and job environment as well (Noe et.al, 1998) also there are more approaches used in job design to increase motivations and efficiency of employees like, job rotation, job enlargement, and job enrichment. According to Dessler, Gary, Hack man & Oldham has developed a pattern of job specification which consists of skills variety, job identity, job importance, job autonomy, feedback, and interaction during performing job [2]. Dessler has suggested an application pattern for job enrichment which is considered as an approach to enhance the job performance [Ibid].

When duties are combined worker need skills variety, and when job unit formulated the worker needs, job identity and job importance, which give him the feeling of job meaningful. Consequently motivating worker, while relation with customers' needs job feedback which resulted in a feeling of work responsibility toward his work outcomes, so when job enrichment pattern is applied. It is proposed by Dessler, Gary, that pattern needs construction of feedback channels to let workers knowing the real results of their works from the point view of customers [2]. In addition to that, these feedback channels give an idea about the employee's turnover ratio and the level of accidents in SHR organizations [7].

Job design dimensions

Job autonomy: job autonomy means giving the employee the freedom to identify some job issues related to his job like, how and when he should carry out his job duties also job autonomy could be the freedom given to an employee in taking decisions related to his work [2]. While Parker, Wall & Jackson, indicate the importance of job autonomy because of the positive relationship between job autonomy and a positive initiative of workers toward their job and the feeling of responsibility [5]. In addition, Lathan & Pinder found that giving the employee more autonomy would let them allocate more time for learning and upgrading their technical level regarding their job [Ibid.].

Task Identity

Task identity is when an employee reaches appoint which enable him to perform the complete job with meaningful results and value [1]. This performance will be linked to employee name who has done it as (Gangne, and Deci, 2005) see this as

very important. On the other hand, according to Hackman & Oldham, when an employee is aware of the importance of his job results, this awareness will be reflected on his behaviour as an apposite reaction toward his job [Ibid.].

Feedback

It is known as the direct and clear information received by an employee about the job he performed, it is important to distinguish between two types of feedback, the first one is related to job specifications and the second one is coming from managers in the form of written or oral feedback [1]. Moreover, feedback is considered as an important issue to employees because it represents an element of satisfaction about their performance, so it acts as a strong motivator for a strong performance [7].

Knowledge Sharing

Knowledge sharing among employees in organizations is considered as a strong element of competitive advantage [8]. It has been that knowledge sharing became one of the deeply rooted concept in employees behaviour in which it may be studied and managed at the organization level, group level, and individual level [9] [10] [11].

On the other hand, when studying knowledge sharing in the organization we have to study the mechanisms of knowledge sharing which includes, employees incentives for knowledge sharing, level of awareness about it, and the interaction between peers in this regard, all these points are essential for achieving knowledge sharing in organizations.

The system is designed to customize the processes of collecting, processing, and disseminating knowledge to maximize the benefits of the practices and technologies implemented in the company. Knowledge management highlighting the collective experience of the company and then its subsequent use, including its distribution and knowledge sharing among all employees of the company works best when it is carried out by the professional organization that most of all need it and for which it, in fact, and intended. Therefore, we can now more accurately define knowledge management. It is important to understand that knowledge is implicit, not directly expressed; they are difficult to single out, and they largely depend on the specific context and therefore make it necessary for the existence of a living community to make full use of all the benefits and benefits that knowledge management can offer.

Job descriptions are the duties of employees of the company. When it is talked about the successful application of the ideas, it is assumed the participation of all employees although, in practice, this is not necessary. Nevertheless, as a rule, most of the company's employees take part in processes [8]. It is believed that in most cases, when it is was successfully implemented, the real impetus to the development of the project was given by the employees themselves, who stated that they were ready to support this project, because then the company

would work better [12]. Therefore, most employees have completely new job responsibilities related to their activities.

The Knowledge Dissemination System is a subsystem of the Knowledge Management and Innovation Management System and is viewed as an IT component or corporate knowledge repository organized using information technology, the web portal and information software provided (Colman, 1990). The owner of the Strategic Human Resource (SHR) management process in the company is the Department of Strategy and Innovation. SHR is a tool to help coordinate the management and knowledge sharing in the Exploration and Production Unit (EBU) for solving technological and production tasks. The system is designed to customize the processes of collecting, processing, and disseminating knowledge to maximize the benefits of the practices and technologies implemented in the company. The module advanced, and new technologies significantly simplified the process of initiating and monitoring the implementation of pilot-industrial tests at the company's fields. Of no less importance is the administration of SHR by experts from professional families and the existence of a culture of experience exchange between employees [13].

Knowledge sharing implies interchanging knowledge among employees by sending and receiving knowledge throughout the organization by relationships between employees, in which all knowledge employed will be accumulated and shared between them [Ibid]. In contrast to that, Szulaski, see that knowledge is something personnel, in which we cannot guarantee that motivating employees can result in knowledge sharing in organizations [12]. Moreover, Cabrera & Cabrera, see that there are some tools which can be employed to enhance knowledge sharing in the organization [13]. In this perspective, many researchers see that rewards programs can make a big difference in order to create the required motivation, in the meantime they always think that job design is a must to make knowledge sharing. They function within the "tides" depending on who their members are, and also according to their interests, commitment and efforts. In this article, we set out our thoughts on the life cycle of the organization - from their formation to disbandment or, in some cases, reform, and revival.

Knowledge management highlighting the collective experience of the company and then its subsequent use, including its distribution and knowledge sharing among all employees of the company works best when it is carried out by the professional organization that most of all need it and for which it, in fact, and intended. Therefore, we can now more accurately define knowledge management. It is important to understand that knowledge is implicit, not directly expressed; they are difficult to single out, and they largely depend on the specific context and therefore make it necessary for the existence of a living community to make full use of all the benefits and benefits that knowledge management can offer. Conversely, the current knowledge management system can in turn "feed" organization that already exist, which just appear and require certain care, and those that are yet to be "planted" so that they can "grow up"

in the future. In this process, knowledge management and community formation form a positive interdependent cycle [14, 15, & 16].

The Internet has had a huge impact on how the work is now done. Now it is much easier to work from a distance. In many firms, virtual teams of employees have become the norm; such groups bring together the best professionals to perform a specific job, no matter where they currently reside. In addition, the virtual organization is formed to work in the field of advanced technological disciplines, to solve various problems and for joint training. As a result, we believe that a correct understanding of the community's life cycle becomes more and more important for organizations.

It is speculated that if one loses the absolute control of the new and exclusive knowledge that it has, it can be used by other people, making one become unimportant or lose its "place of exclusivity as unique. For this population, it is not so difficult to formulate hypothetical answers that would solve our problem. It is the fear of ceasing to be indispensable that makes them selfish and not transferring their new knowledge, which may be for him, but not for others [17]. The real fear, in this unprofessional attitude and most of the times covert, is to share knowledge with internal competition. The formalization of job descriptions, tasks, and responsibilities seems to make employees believe that they are dispensable, that any new person, with specific training, taking for granted a true process of selection of integral personnel (taking the same way technical aspects such as their interests, motivations, values, for an adaptation of cultures) could take their place.

Knowledge sharing Motivations

Intrinsic motivations: Intrinsic motivation is known as the internal sight of an employee of his performed activities. It would be enjoyable and importance, some psychological researches reveal that subordinates who have intrinsic motivations toward their work have more initiatives and indulgent, which contribute in upgrading their technical and functional level and self-development [18, 19, & 20]. In this sense, other studies also reveal that intrinsic motivations enhance the positive behaviour of employees like innovation, creativity, learning, and a high-quality product [21]. Additionally, it is logical to expect that intrinsic motivations have a positive impact on knowledge sharing as other learning activities. In addition to these findings, they see that the effect of motivational factors clear in developing employee self-capabilities and consequently increasing their need for knowledge in which making them seek knowledge sharing [22] [23] [24].

Introjected Motivation: Employees who have introjected motivations are more concerned about their position in their society, this feeling of concern making them try to work hard to achieve more success in their work [25]. It has been identified that good job results are highly appreciated and it is becoming one of the main motivations for job accomplishment. Therefore,

introjected motivations of employees has a great social value in which it is positively correlated with knowledge sharing, because employee always endeavor to accomplish his work correctly in order to get reward and appreciation for that, employees need knowledge, this needed knowledge can be acquired from other employees, in return for that he can give his knowledge to them, and by doing so knowledge sharing occurs in organization [26] [27] [28].

External motivations: External motivations for knowledge sharing are considered as important factors, these factors push employees toward their jobs. According to Vroom, (1964) theory of expectation, people expectations of gain and losses are built upon personnel estimations. The motivation for knowledge sharing is essential to get benefits to the person who needs it, in addition, formal performance appraisal is very important to employees, it represents a feedback about their performance which is positively correlated with knowledge sharing [29, 30, 31, & 32]. For that employee who is motivated externally to share knowledge is seeking knowledge sharing because he thinks that he will get a more valued return, therefore any employee who wants to get more knowledge he has to give knowledge to others in return, consequently knowledge sharing is achieved in the organization [33].

Job autonomy and knowledge sharing

Autonomy in the job is one specification which considered being one of the factors that put employee under responsibility toward his job, in general autonomy or freedom to carry out work considered to be as a mechanism of motivation for employees and therefore improving their performance [34] [35] [36] [37]. The autonomy in work has a positive effect on motivation toward employees work and duties, in this aspect a debate is concentrated around three basic psychological needs of all employees.

These needs are efficiency, autonomy, and social relationships, when these needs are satisfied employee becomes motivated toward his job. The importance of job autonomy to enhance interjected motivation [38]. The autonomy in work has a strong correlation with voluntary social indulgence by students, this indicates the positive relationship between job autonomy and the basic introjected motivations of employees toward knowledge sharing.

Task identity and knowledge sharing

Task identity is a job element that leads to self-motivation of employees, it happens when employees feel that they will understand their job duties and these duties will lead to the accomplishment of their work [Ibid]. This include producing a product independently, after achieving that, employees will have the feeling of their performance value ,as a task identity it is linked to freedom in planning and implementing the task by the same employee in an appropriate way ,employee feels that others are expecting him to give his best performance, as a result he will try to do his job perfectly [39] [40].

Previous studies:

The study conducted, entitled Effect of organizational culture in knowledge management from managers point view in Jordanian ministries [41]. The study aimed at identifying the extent to which knowledge management is applied in the Jordanian ministries, in addition to identifying the impact of the different organizational culture on knowledge management in the Jordanian ministries. The study reached the following results: A statistically significant relationship between organizational culture and knowledge management in Jordanian ministries while there were no statistically significant differences in the effect of organizational culture on knowledge management due to all organizational variables.

Another study aimed at shedding light on the relationship between knowledge society and knowledge work through a field study that illustrates the nature of this relationship in the Jordanian financial sector [42]. The study results, reveal that a strong and statistically significant relationship between the indicators of knowledge society and cognitive work, also the existence of a significant effect between the indicators of the knowledge society and knowledge work as any changes that occur in the indicators of the research community lead to influence the variables of knowledge work

Moreover, the study was conducted in the research and development departments of companies that adopt advanced technology in their work and use the knowledge widely in Taiwan. The study assumes that knowledge staff has the ability to share knowledge with them if they have the required degree of satisfaction [43]. In which staff work is an environment of friendliness and friendship as well as satisfying their intrinsic incentives. The study has shown a positive correlation between the friendly work environment and satisfaction of intrinsic incentives on the one hand and the sharing of knowledge.

The study aimed at identifying the level of participation of organizations in identifying and determining the reasons why employees share knowledge with them [44]. The study was conducted on (48) employees working in 13 construction companies, real estate development companies, and other multinational companies. The study reveals a positive correlation between ranges of incentives intrinsic incentives, global motivations, social incentives, and participatory knowledge. Social factors included compliance with organizational culture rules, imitation of the tradition of leader behaviour, moral commitment in sharing knowledge and awareness of the value of organizational knowledge.

Finally, the study aimed at examining the degree of knowledge sharing among medical personnel in Taiwan during the SARS 2003 outbreak [45]. The study was conducted between August and December 2005. The results of the study showed a positive correlation between knowledge sharing among medical staff and professional commitment. The study showed that it is possible to retain medical staff by encouraging them to share knowledge, which helps to increase professional commitment and thus reduce the effects of epidemics.

3. RESEARCH METHOD AND ANALYSIS

Study population

The study targeted Jordanian public and private hospitals located in Irbid Governorate, north of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. The number of public hospitals affiliated to the Ministry of Health is seven hospitals and one Royal Medical Service hospital [46] [47]. The number of private hospitals in the study was six hospitals; a random sample of the study population was collected, with a sample size of 50 persons, which includes physicians, nurses, laboratory technicians, and radiologists.

Unit of Analysis

There are different units of analysis in this study. These include the doctors, nurses, radiologists, and laboratory technicians in the hospitals covered to achieve the research objectives.

Data sources

This study was based on two types of data: secondary data, which collected through revision of theoretical literature in books, periodicals and published researches on the subject of work design and knowledge sharing. The primary data were obtained and collected by the study tool (questionnaire). The research questionnaire was developed preliminarily, containing vocabulary obtained and modified from the literature review and previous studies related to the subject job design and work incentives to share knowledge among employees [48]. The tool consisted of 23 questions divided into two parts, as follows:

Part I: This section includes the personal characteristics of the study sample members such as gender, age, occupation, years of experience, career status

Part 2: This part of the questionnaire includes the paragraphs related to the study variables

Paragraph (1.2) is about the sources of knowledge received by the employee Paragraph (3.4) includes the entity to which the employee is sent the knowledge. Paragraphs (5, 6, 7) measuring the level of intrinsic motivations towards knowledge sharing among employees. Paragraphs (8, 9, and 10) measure the level of instilled incentives in employees (Introjected Motivation) towards sharing knowledge. Paragraphs 11,12,13,14 measures (External Motivation) towards participatory work, while paragraphs (15, 16, and 17) measure the level of independence of work. Paragraphs (18, 19, and 20) measure the characteristics of the task identity. Paragraphs (21, 22, 23, and 24) measure the level of feedback from work. The questionnaire was distributed directly to the study sample.

Verification of the study tool

To verify the stability of the study tool, the equation of (Cronbach Alpha) was applied to all paragraphs of the study.

Study element	Number of paragraphs	Coefficient of stability
Knowledge sharing	4	0.75
Job design	19	0.76
Total	23	0.75

Table 1: stability coefficients of the study elements

Table no. (1) Shows Stability coefficients of Cronbach Alfa stability test for the fields of study (n = 44). Table no.1 shows the coefficient of stability of the study fields, which include (knowledge sharing, .075, job design .076). The coefficient of stability of the instrument as a whole is (0.75), and the aggregate values are acceptable for the application. Most studies indicated that the coefficient of acceptance of the stability coefficient is (0.60) [46].

The study sample:

The sample of the study consisted of (44) employees and Jordanian hospitals the sample was randomly selected from the study population. Table (2) shows the distribution of the sample members according to a personal variable.

4. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Part I: Demographics section

Table 2: Distribution of study sample members according to personal variables (n = 44).

Variable	Level	Frequency	Percentage
sex	male	26	59.1
	female	18	40.9
	total	44	100%
Age	25-34	19	43.2
	35-44	19	43.2
	45-54	6	13.6
	total	44	100%
Qualification	diploma	5	11.4
	B.A	39	88.6
	High degree		
	total	44	100%
Years of experience	Less than 5 years	9	20.5
	5-9 years	11	25
	10-15 years	15	34.1
	More than 15 years	9	20.5
	total	44	100%
Profession	Doctor	9	20.5
	Nurse	23	52.3
	Radiologist	5	11.4
	Lab technician	7	15.4

	Total	44	
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Table no. 2 shows the males in the sample represents (59.1%), while the females represent (40.9%). The highest percentage of the distribution of the sample was according to the age variable was (43.2%) for each age group (25-34 years, 35-44 years) and the lowest percentage (13.6%) for the age group of (45-54 years). The highest percentage of the distribution of sample members according to the variable of a number of years of experience (34.1%) was for the experience of (10-15 years), while the lowest percentage (20.5%) for each period of experience (less than 5 years). The highest percentage of the distribution of the sample was according to the profession variable (52.3%) for (nurses), while the lowest percentage (11.4%) for the profession (laboratory technicians).

Part II: Results of the statistical analysis and test hypotheses of the study

This section presents the results of the statistical analysis of the study, which aims to identify the job design and its dimensions as motivation and the impact of knowledge sharing among the employees in Jordanian hospitals. The results will be presented by reviewing the statistical averages and standard deviations of the fields of study.

The above below shows that means for the fields of study ranged from (3.70-4.02), where the highest is paragraph (1) "My work has the opportunity to undertake independent initiatives" with a high rating, while the lowest goes for paragraph (2) With a medium rating and the overall arithmetic mean of the field is (3.89) which is high.

Table 3: Means and standard deviations of the responses of the sample members of the study on the areas of field of knowledge sharing, ranked descending

No.	Item	Arithmetic mean	STD	Rank	Valuation degree
1	I have the opportunity to undertake independent initiatives	4.02	0.90	1	High
2	There is a great diversity in my work	3.95	0.86	2	High
3	I have the opportunity to complete the work that I have started	3.89	0.75	3	High

4	My job is characterized by freedom in the way I do it	3.7	1.05	4	Medium
5	Knowledge sharing	3.89	0.63		High

Means of the overall job design field ranged from 2.25 to 3.80, where the highest level was of intrinsic incentive followed by the moral incentives and task independence level with an average of 3.65 and a higher rating, was for external incentives with a mean of (3.59) and an average rating, in fourth place job feedback with a mean of (2.36) with an average rating, and in the last position is the task identity with a mean of 2.25 and low rating, the mean of job design field as a whole is (3.24) with medium evaluation. Next is the statistical averages and the standard deviations of responses of the sample are presented below for each dimension of job design.

Table 4: Dimensions of the field of work design, means and standard deviations of the responses.

No.	Dimension	mean	Standard deviation	rank	rating
1	Core level of incentives	3.8	0.55	high	1
2	Level of moral incentives	3.65	0.65	medium	2
4	Job independence	3.65	0.65	medium	2
3	External incentives	3.59	0.63	medium	4
6	Feedback	2.36	1.11	medium	5
5	Task identity	2.25	1.06	low	6
	Job design	3.24	0.39	medium	

Table 4: Means and standard deviations of responses of the study sample members on paragraphs dimensions of intrinsic incentives in descending order.

Grade	Rank	Std. deviation	mean	paragraph	no
high	1	0.93	3.82	I have the opportunity to perform work from A-Z	1
high	2	0.90	3.81	I have the opportunity to do my job independently	2
high	3	0.82	3.8	Receive consistently official notifications about my work	3

The above table shows that the averages of paragraphs about the level of intrinsic incentives ranged between 3.80-3.82 with a high rating for all paragraphs, the highest one was paragraph (1) "I have the opportunity to perform the work from beginning to end", while the lowest paragraph (3) "I'm constantly receiving official notifications about work."

Table 6: Means and standard deviations of the responses of study sample members on paragraphs of the level of moral incentives in descending order (N = 44).

Grade	Rank	Std. Dev.	Mean	Paragraph	No
high	1	0.93	3.82	I have the opportunity to perform work from A-Z	1
high	2	0.90	3.81	I have the opportunity to do my job independently	2
high	3	0.82	3.8	Receive consistently official notifications about my work	3

The above table shows that the means for paragraphs of the level of external incentives ranged from (3.25-4.02). moreover, it is identified that "I give knowledge available to my workmates in my department" have a high rating " while "My work peers always use the knowledge I gave to them at work " have a medium rating.

Table 7: Means and standard deviations of responses of the sample members on paragraphs for external incentives in descending order

Grade	Rank	Std. Dev	Mean	Paragraph	No.
high	1	0.95	4.02	I give knowledge available to my workmates in my department	2
medium	2	0.98	3.55	I use the knowledge from workmates in doing my job	1
medium	3	0.85	3.52	I share my knowledge because I think it is important to my job	4
medium	4	4.92	3.25	My work peers always use the knowledge I gave to them at work	3

The above table shows that the means for paragraphs about the levels of moral incentives ranged from (3.50 to 3.91), where the top was for paragraph (3)I get knowledge from work peers with a high rating, while the lowest was paragraph (2) I receive feedback Regularly from my staff "with a medium rating.

Table 5: Means and standard deviations of sample responses about job autonomy paragraphs in descending order

No.	Paragraph	Mean	Std. Dev.	Rank	Grade
2	I share my knowledge to show that I am competent	2.57	1.19	1	medium
1	I share my knowledge to show a good impression to my supervisor	2.36	1.31	2	medium
3	I share my knowledge for praising by officials	1.82	1.04	3	low

The above table shows the means for paragraphs job autonomy ranged from (3.43-3.77), where the top is paragraph (1) "I share my knowledge because I feel satisfied " with a high rating, while the lowest paragraph is no. (3) I share knowledge with peers because I feel proud of myself when I do with a medium range.

Table 9: Means and standard deviations of the responses of the study sample for task identity in descending order

No.	Paragraph	Mean	Std. Dev	Rank	Grade
2	I share my knowledge to show that I am competent	2.57	1.19	1	medium
1	I share my knowledge to show a good impression to my supervisor	2.36	1.31	2	medium
3	I share my knowledge for praising by officials	1.82	1.04	3	low

The above table shows that means for task identity ranged from 1.82-2.57. In this sense, "I share knowledge with my colleagues to show my colleagues that I am proficient and knowledgeable" with an average rating, while "I share my knowledge for praise by officials" with a low rating.

Table 6: Means and standard deviations of the study sample responses for Paragraphs of job feedback in descending order

Grade	Rank	Std. Dev.	Mean	Paragraph	No.
Low	1	1.41	2.68	I share my knowledge with colleagues because it helps me get promoted	3
Medium	2	1.2	2.36	I share knowledge with peers for reward purpose	1
medium	3	1.03	2.05	I share my knowledge with colleagues for praise and praise by coworkers	2

The above table no. (10) Shows that paragraph no.3 (I share my knowledge with colleagues because it helps me get promoted) has a mean of (2.68) which is the highest among feedback paragraphs with a low rating, while paragraph no.2 has the lowest mean with a medium rating.

The results of the main hypothesis test are as follows: There is no statistically significant effect at the level of ($\alpha = .05$), of job design dimensions on knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals. To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the regression equation was applied to study the effect of the

dimensions of job design on knowledge sharing. Table (11) shows that there is a statistically significant effect at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) the correlation coefficient (R) (0.54) is statistically significant and indicates the degree of statistical correlation between the dimensions of the job design and the knowledge sharing. R-square (0.28) is a statistical function value that explains the ability of the job design dimensions to affect the value of the test (F) (2.49) was statistically significant (0.00), which is a statistically significant value at level of Significance ($0.05 = \alpha$) indicates that there is a statistically significant relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, thus accepting the alternative hypothesis and rejecting the null hypothesis.

Table 7: Results of the application of multiple regression equations to examine the effect of the of the work design dimensions on knowledge sharing

SIG	F	R2	R	Dimension
Relationship in between job design dimensions and knowledge sharing	0.00	2.49	0.28	0.54

The first sub-hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of significance ($0.05 = \alpha$) of the relationship between job autonomy as an internal incentive and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals. To validate this hypothesis, the regression equation was applied to examine the effect of internal incentives on the relationship between knowledge sharing and job autonomy, among employees in Jordanian hospitals. As it is illustrated in Table 12.

Table 8: The relationship between job autonomy as an internal incentive and sharing of knowledge among workers in Jordanian hospitals (N = 44)

SIG	F	R2	R	T	Dimension
Relationship between Job autonomy and knowledge sharing	0.00	77.92	0.65	0.81	8.83

Table (12), Shows a statistically significant correlation between knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospital and job autonomy and internal incentives. The correlation coefficient (R) was (0.81), which is statistically significant and indicates the degree of correlation. The value of the test (F) (77.92) was statistically significant (0.00), while (R2) value was (0.65) This is a statistically significant value at ($\alpha = 0.05$) which indicates the impact with statistically significant at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) of the independence of the internal incentives on knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals, thus accepting the alternative hypothesis and rejecting the null hypothesis.

The second sub-hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the significance level ($0.05 = \alpha$) between task identity of the as a moral incentive and the knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals: To verify the validity of this hypothesis the regression equation was applied to examine the effect of moral incentives on the relationship between Knowledge sharing and Task Identity, among employees in Jordanian hospitals.

Table 9: Significance

sig	F	R2	R	T	Dimension
The relationship between the identity of the task as a moral incentive and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals	0.00	8.44	0.17	0.93-	2.93

Table (13), shows a statistically significant relationship at the significance level ($0.05 = \alpha$) between the task identity as a moral incentive and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals. The correlation coefficient (R) was 0.17, the value of R-square was (0.41) and statistically significant. The significance of task identity was interpreted as a significant influence on knowledge sharing. The value of test (F) (8.64)) in statistical terms (0.00), which is a statistically significant value at the level of d ($0.05 = \alpha$), which indicates a statistically significant effect at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) on the relationship between the task identity and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted in the alternative formula and rejects the null hypothesis.

Sub-Hypothesis no.3: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the job feedback as an external incentive and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals. To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the regression equation was applied to study the effect of job feedback as an external catalyst on knowledge sharing among workers in Jordanian hospitals.

Table (14), shows a statistically significant relationship at the level of significance ($0.05 = \alpha$) between the feedback as an external incentive and the knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals. The correlation coefficient (R) was 0.37. The value of R2 (0.37) was statistically significant. The significance of the task identity was expressed as an external incentive for knowledge sharing. The value of (F) test was (6.68), and significant regarding Statistical (0.01) is statistically significant value at $\alpha = 0.05$ ($A = 0.05$) on the relation between feedback as an external incentive and knowledge sharing among workers in Jordanian hospitals. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted in the alternative formula and rejects the null hypothesis.

Table 10: Significance Relationship

SIG	R2	R	T	Job dimension
The relationship between feedback as an external catalyst and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals	0.01	0.13	0.37	2.58

The results of the first sub-hypothesis test related to the effect of job autonomy as one dimension of the work design showed that there is a statistically significant effect of this dimension on the sharing of knowledge among the employees, and job autonomy motivates employees to perform well and achieve goals. Also job autonomy make employees willing to search for the knowledge that enables him to achieve his goals, especially the knowledge of his peers and therefore the good design of the work, which takes into account the job autonomy of the employee in performing his tasks and completion of his work assigned to them, so this type of job design inspire employees to share the knowledge they have.

The second sub-hypothesis test showed a statistically significant effect of the task in motivating employees to share knowledge among employees in Jordanian hospitals in the north of the Kingdom, and since the employee knows the task he is performing, he has to do his job well. It naturally needs the necessary knowledge, and this explains the impact of task identity as a catalyst for sharing knowledge among staff where the employee seeks to obtain the necessary knowledge from the work colleagues in the organization.

The third hypothesis test showed the existence of feedback as one of the dimensions of the design of the work on the sharing of knowledge among the employees of Jordanian hospitals in the north of the Kingdom. Since the feedback from the work is an assessment of the performance of the employee doing the work, the employee is keen to have this feedback For working at the best level and this requires that the work carried out on a high quality that comes from high knowledge of the employee, and thus seek the employee to obtain the knowledge that enables him to achieve this, especially from work colleagues who work with them in the same place.

5. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to achieve following research objectives:

- To identify the level of relationship between job design elements and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals
- To explore the level of relationship between job autonomy and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals
- To analyze the level of relationship between task identity and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals
- To examine the level of relationship between job feedback and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals

On the basis of analysis conducted above, the hypothesis test showed a set of results, the results of the main hypothesis of the study showed a statistically significant effect between the dimensions of the work design (independence, identity of the task and feedback) and knowledge sharing among employees in Jordanian hospitals in Irbid governorate, north of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. These dimensions work as an incentive for employees to get the knowledge they need from their peers.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, a set of proposed recommendations were identified for inclusion by the organizations' administrations, whether they were in the public sector or the private sector. The departments in the organizations should pay greater attention to the design of the work so that the work design includes the main dimensions of the work, which act as catalysts for the search for knowledge to ensure the process of increasing the interaction between the employees regarding giving and taking knowledge among themselves.

It is recommended to give employees greater autonomy in work, especially in the work that requires it, which reflects positively on the strength of internal incentives and enable them to obtain the required knowledge. Moreover, it is also recommended to encourage employees to do their work fully and without fragmentation, which reflects positively on the employee and his sense of the value of work and responsibility, so seeking to get the knowledge to complete the functions of his job fully.

Another recommendation of this study would be to ensure that employees understand that feedback as a dimension of the work design is that it is not a means of control as much as a means of continuous improvement. It is reflected positively on the employee in his quest to obtain the knowledge required to improve its performance, which positively affects the feedback on the performance of work done by the employee.

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